

Position paper

On the discussion for welfare improvement in farmed fish. Recommendations from GRINNAQUA's consortium.

Marine and freshwater aquaculture is responsible for putting more than 120 billion animals¹ to the market each year while remaining one of the fastest growing industries. Production levels are expected to reach massive numbers, by far exceeding any terrestrial farmed animal production. Nonetheless, European production, in its majority characterized by the production of rainbow trout, carps, sturgeon, Atlantic salmon, gilthead seabream, and European seabass, as well as flatfish species like turbot and Senegalese sole, only represents 20% of global fish production². While important efforts have been made by the EU to improve those numbers, concerns about the industry have been raised by society, with the consumers being especially concerned with the welfare of animals being produced.

Despite the increase in production levels, the Portuguese piece of the pie in EU context is nevertheless relatively small, being only the 16th main producer among the EU member states, representing 1 % of production in terms of volume³.

The question remains, how much consideration has been paid to animal welfare whilst capitalising on EU stimulus to improve production numbers?

The EU recognises fishes as sentient beings and commits itself to ensure animal welfare when formulating and implementing the Union's policies in certain key areas, such as animals bred and kept for farming. As such, the EU has defined strategies on its policies regarding the minimum standards under which aquatic animals are allowed to be farmed.

However, this remains a relatively new and rapidly changing field, with room for improvement in many areas. The GRINNAQUA consortium proposes strategies to improve fish welfare during both defined time-points of the production chain (e.g., transport and slaughter) and through the entire farming cycle.

- Effective management of fish welfare must address the complexities of optimal husbandry conditions and needs across various species and rearing systems, each with unique characteristics. Specific guidelines should be developed for each commercial species, taking into account the distinct attributes of semi-intensive, intensive, and recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS).

¹ Mood, A., Lara, E., Boyland, N. K., & Brooke, P. (2023). Estimating global numbers of farmed fishes killed for food annually from 1990 to 2019. *Animal Welfare*, 32, e12. doi:10.1017/awf.2023.4

² EU Commission (2017c) Welfare of farmed fish: Common practices during transport and at slaughter. Final report. 21. doi: 10.2875/708396

³ European Commission: Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, The EU fish market – 2021 edition, Publications Office of the European Union, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2771/563899>

- Public awareness regarding the welfare standards in aquatic animal production remains limited and is often skewed by a minor number of negative welfare events. To address the insufficient social acceptance of this industry and its products, targeted educational programs at schools and public media are essential. A recent workshop on fish welfare in aquaculture (<https://grinnaqua.eu/news/fish-welfare/#next>) with the presence of members from academia as well as industrial partners such as aquaculture producers and feed industry, highlighted the challenges of misinformation and the difficulties in reaching awareness of the general public. It is crucial to communicate aquaculture's role in supporting needs of a growing global population and to clarify actual production conditions. Moreover, allowing public access to the industry to showcase best practices is vital for fostering social acceptance.

- Producers are increasingly recognizing the moral and economic importance of maintaining animal welfare throughout the production cycle, especially during critical handling procedures such as transport, vaccination, grading and slaughter. However, effective and timely methods to assess welfare in production settings is partly missing. E.g., there is a trend to push farmers towards more sensitive ways of slaughtering such as electric shock, but this technology although very promising is not fully effective for all species and its use requires careful validation.

- Research into minimally invasive welfare assessment tools, along with new technologies like biosensors, AI, and predictive analytics, could significantly enhance welfare monitoring.

- Implementing and validating new technologies will require time and investment from both the research community and farming companies. Ultimately, these advancements could minimize manual handling, anticipate challenges, reduce stress for animals, and diminish the reliance on therapeutics by proactively preventing disease.

- Disease management in farmed fish is a major concern, often linked to poor environmental conditions, inadequate management, and stress. These challenges have prompted significant investment from researchers and producers. However, there is a limited availability of licensed veterinary medicines and feed additives, such as probiotics. The urgent need for new treatments, especially for sea lice infestations in salmon, underscores the necessity of finding alternatives to stressful and costly interventions like thermal treatments.

- A comprehensive national disease management program is needed to identify and predict outbreaks at a local level. While such a program exists in theory, it has yet to be fully implemented within the Portuguese industry. The industry requires more data and knowledge to enhance animal health and welfare, and collaboration with academia, supported by government initiatives, can help achieve this.

- Climate change poses a significant threat to farmed animals, potentially leading to intensified stress responses. Recent EFSA reports have raised concerns about

Vibrio infections, which not only affect humans consuming raw or undercooked bivalves but also pose a risk to the aquacultured species due to the increased prevalence and diversity of *Vibrio spp*⁴ present in European waters. This situation demands enhanced understanding of species resilience and the selection of farmed animals better suited to adapt to changing environmental conditions. Inter-sectoral collaboration between industry and academia is essential to address these challenges.

- Related to the latest point, the acceptance of gene-edited organisms may offer solutions in scenarios where animal welfare is severely compromised, and other interventions are insufficient. For instance, an edited variant of Atlantic salmon that could achieve total resistance to sea lice would improve not only animal health and welfare in a production setting but also reduce sea lice prevalence in the environment, thus benefiting wild populations.
- Finally, we believe robust discussion is needed within the European Union and associated countries about the expectations placed on farmers regarding high welfare standards, especially while importing large quantities of non-EU products farmed under uncertain conditions and lower quality standards. Consumers should be informed about the production processes behind their food, enabling them to make informed choices regarding species and products that obey to high welfare standards.

About GRINNAQUA consortium

GRINNAQUA (GA n. 101079467) is a funded project of the European Union under the program HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03. This project is composed by four institutions with a high background on aquaculture research: Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research of the University of Porto (CIIMAR, Portugal), University of Bergen (UiB, Norway), Roslin Institute from the University of Edinburgh (United Kingdom) and the National Institute of Agricultural and Food Research and Technology from the National Centre integrated into the State Agency Higher Council for Scientific Research (INIA-CSIC, Spain). All partners have joined forces in this challenging project to improve the health of farmed fish through a deeper knowledge on vaccination, novel nutraceutical strategies, genomics as well as disease prevention and welfare. Also, an important task on researchers training was developed with a high quantity of resources in the website.

The Project Coordination Committee and Management Team is composed by Benjamín Costas (also project coordinator), Marina Machado, Sergio Fernández-Boo, Tânia Pereira, Rita Azeredo & Lourenço Ramos-Pinto from CIIMAR, Frank Nilsen and Aina-Cathrine Øvergård from UiB, Diego Robledo and Tim Bean from Roslin Institute and Carolina Tafalla and Patricia Díaz-Rosales from INIA CSIC.

This document was written by Marina Machado and Sergio Fernández-Boo and reviewed by the PCC members.

⁴ EFSA BIOHAZ Panel (EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards), Koutsoumanis, K., Allende, A., Alvarez Ordóñez, A., Bolton, D., Bover-Cid, S., Chemaly, M., De Cesare, A., Herman, L., Hilbert, F., Lindqvist, R., Nauta, M., Nonno, R., Peixe, L., Ru, G., Simmons, M., Skandamis, P., Baker-Austin, C., Hervio-Heath, D., ... Suffredini, E. (2024). Public health aspects of *Vibrio spp.* related to the consumption of seafood in the EU. *EFSA Journal*, 22(7), e8896. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2024.8896>

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